

THE STABILITY ANALYSIS OF PREVAILING RETAINING WALLS VARIATION DESIGN IN DIFFERENT SLOPE

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Abstract:

Landslides are common hazard on slopes often triggered by factors such as soil composition slope load and ground water prese Nce .One effective solution to mitigate this risk is the use of retaining wall, which serve as a structural reinforcements for slope.

In the case of conventional gravity retaining walls,the stability of the structure depends significantly on its weight,which in turn Is determine by the dimensions. Typically,this dimensions are established through a trial-and-error process. If the retaining wall Is insufficient to withstand the load its dimentions must be adjusted accordingly. This study focuses on analyzing conventional

Gravity retaining walls with various design variations applied to a 3-meter vertical slopes. The analysis considers a scenario Where two cohesive soil layers are present behind the retaining walls and the structure relies solely on its weight for stability.by Examining the dynamic bond between the weight of the retaining wall and its stability, the study aims to determining the most

Suitable retaining wall design for this specific slope condition. The findings indicate that increasing the weight of the retaining Wall enhances its safety factor. Furthermore, a retaining wall design with a sloped front face achieves a higher safety factor Compared to a slender-shaped design

Keywords - Stability Analysis, Soil, Retaining Wall, Slope.

I. INTRODUCTION

The earthwork behind the retaining wall undergoes gradually deforms and separates from the stationary soil, forming a slip surface with a complex shape influenced by the wall's movement mode and surface roughness. This research examines the behavior of a Immovable retaining wall subjected to a uniform surcharge along a horizontal backfill under active translation mode, analyzed within a two-dimensional equilibrium system. Using Janssen's approach, exact stress solutions are generalized in rectangular coordinates and validated against boundary conditions on the retaining wall and the Coulomb slip line behind it. The analysis reveals an arching effect, as maximum stresses occur not at the toe but at a certain distance away from it. The proposed formulations are validated through

comparisons with full-scale and laboratory-scale experimental data Design approaches for reinforced-soil retaining walls with cohesionless soil backfill have been well-established.

During construction, the compacted soil in the reinforced wall is typically unsaturated, meaning the apparent cohesion resulting from soil mineralogy and suction can contribute significantly to stability. This study investigates two methods for incorporating the effects of suction into existing design standards based on slope stability analysis: the simplified method and the simplified stiffness method. These approaches were evaluated using a case study of a geosynthetically reinforced soil retaining wall Slope Stability – Bishop’s Method for Stability

Introducing in 1955 by Alan Wilfred Bishop of Imperial College London, the Bishop method stands out as a notable Advancement in its domain several slice - based techniques Used to evaluate slope stability and determine the factor of safety (FOS). In this method shear forces acting on the side surfaces of each slice can be disregarded, meaning

$$V_{i-1} = V_i + 1V_{i+1} = V_{i+1} \quad V_{i-1} = V_i + 1.$$

Where, Forces acting on a single slice:

- a) the weight of the soil above the failure surface W,
- b) the interslice reactions from the adjacent slices X_{i-1} , X_{i+1} , V_{i-1} , V_{i+1} ,
- c) The behavior of the stable ground defined by its normal effective N' and a shear component T
- d) the boundary water force U. Bishop method suggests that the shear interslice forces can be neglected, i.e., $V_{i-1} - V_{i+1} = 0$.

To develop his method, Bishop utilized 3 major equilibrium equations:

1. Moment equilibrium for the entire surface of failure with respect to the centre of rotation,
2. Horizontal force equilibrium for the overall surface of failure, and
3. Vertical force equilibriums for each slice.

Formula:

Figure 02: Diagram for FOS

$$FoS = \sum \left\{ \frac{[(c * B + W(1 - r_u) * \tan(\phi))] \sec(\alpha)}{1 + \left[\frac{\tan(\alpha) \tan(\phi)}{FoS} \right]} \right\} \frac{1}{\sum W * \sin(\alpha)}$$

Research has shown that the Bishop method yields reliable results for slope Factor of Safety (FoS) calculations, with negligible variations. Zhu observes that the method's accuracy is on par with advanced techniques, such as the Spencer method. while researchers have not fully understood the theoretical causes of this phenomenon. Spencer (1967) mentioned that the FoS is insensitive to the

inclination of the interslice forces, hence the assumptions of the Bishop method do not highly impact the results.

Figure 03: Site images of Soil

Figure 04: Site images of Soil

Figure 04: PCC for Retaining Wall

II. SITE DETAILS

701 km Mumbai Expressway by MSRDC by MSRDC is an under construction 6 lane access-controlled road with a route alignment connecting Village Shivmadka in Nagpur District to Village Amne in Thane District. Samruddhi Mahamarg will be opened / inaugurated in 2022. The first phase (502 km) will connect Nagpur – Shirdi. Approximately 20 Km toward Jalna, from Aurangabad – Maharashtra.

Figure 05: Cross-Section of 4m Retaining Wall

Design Data

Top level of retaining wall = 4.000 m Ground level = 0.810 m

Founding Level = 0.000 m HFL level = 0.810 m

Total Height from top of wall to founding level = 4.000 m Terrain Slope Behind Construction = 27.57°

Density of concrete = 2.55 t/m³ Density of earth = 2.10 t/m³ Density of water = 1.10 t/m⁴ Surcharge

Slope = 41°

Submerged Unit wt. of concrete = 1.51 t/m³ Submerged Density of earth = 1.10 t/m³ Saturated Density

of earth = 2.21 t/m⁴ Coefficient of base friction = 0.8 Clear cover to Reinforcement = 0.051 m Clear

cover to Reinforcement for foundations = 0.085 m Safe bearing capacity = 31.00 t/m² Unit weight of

Concrete = 2.55 T/m³

Dry Unit weight of Soil = 2.10 T/m³

Submerged Unit weight of Concrete = 1.60 T/m³ Submerged Unit weight of soil = 1.01 T/m³

Saturated Unit weight of soil = 2.30 T/m⁴

Total length of Return wall = 1.01 m Supported part of Return wall = 1.01 m

Angle of internal friction of soil, $f = 30 \text{ deg} = 0.624 \text{ rad}$ Angle of wall friction, $d = 30 \text{ deg} = 0.449 \text{ rad}$
 Angle of inclination of soil at back, $i = 0.000 \text{ deg} = 0.000 \text{ rad}$ Angle of inclination of stem at back, $a = 90 \text{ deg} = 1.671 \text{ rad}$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental Program

In this research, various tests were conducted, including the Modified Proctor Test, Atterberg Limits, and Particle Size Analysis.

1. Modified Proctor Test

Optimum Moisture Content for given soil sample is 6.90 % and Maximum Dry Density is 1.855 gm/cc.

Figure 06: Graph for OMC and MDD

2. Atterberg Limit

Liquid Limit for given soil sample is 33.10% and Plastic Limit is (Non-Plastic) due to sandy soil and Plasticity Index is Null for this soil sample.

Figure 07: Liquid Limit Graph

3. Free Swell Index

Sample Number	Volume in Water After 24hrs of swell (VW)cc.	Volume in Kerosene After 24hrs of swell (VK)cc.	Free Swell Index $[(VW - VK)/VK] \times 100\%$
1	12	11	11
2	13	11	21
Average			16

Free swell index for given soil sample is 15%.

4. California Bearing Ratio

Mould Number	Corrected Unit Load in Kgs		CBR %		CBR % Reported
	2.6mm	5.1mm	2.6mm	5.1mm	
1	182	344	14.21	17.69	
2	204	365	14.04	17.95	
3	191	348	14.07	16.94	
Average CBR Value					17.22%

California Bearing Ratio (CBR) for given soil sample is 17.19z

5. Shear force and Bending moment

6. Slope Stability (Bishop Method)

Figure 09: Slope Stability Verification by Bishop Method

7. Stability Check

Figure 08: SFD and BMD for Retaining wall

Figure 10: Stability Check by Bishop Method

8. Forces Summary Table

Forces Summary for Basic Combination for SLS Check - Quasi Perm Combination									
Member	Location	Section	Distance (m)	Upward Base Pressure	Downward Base Pressure	Net Base Pressure (T/sqm)	Bending Moment (kN.m)	Nature of Moment	
Toe Slab	Edge of the Toe	1-1	0.00	8.856	1.800	7.056	0.000	Sagging	
	Mid of the Toe	2-2	0.30	8.617	1.800	6.817	3.080	Sagging	
	Face of the Stem	3-3	0.60	8.378	1.800	6.578	12.178	Sagging	
Heel Slab	Face of the stem	4-4	1.15	7.940	8.200	-0.260	9.655	Hogging	
	Mid of the Heel	5-5	1.85	7.382	8.200	-0.818	2.861	Hogging	
	Edge of the Heel	6-6	2.55	6.824	8.200	-1.376	0.000	Hogging	
Stem Wall	Top of the stem	7-7	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	Sagging	
	Start of the Tapered	Earth Pres	8-8	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Sagging
		LL Surcharge		1.20	0.000	0.000	0.000		
	Mid of the Tapered	Earth Pres	9-9	1.80	1.070	0.963	0.756	7.144	Sagging
		LL Surcharge		1.20	0.000	0.000	0.900		
	Face of the Heel/Toe	Earth Pres	10-10	3.60	2.141	3.853	1.512	57.153	Sagging
		LL Surcharge		1.20	0.000	0.000	1.800		

V. CONCLUSION

In this research we performed test on soil sample collected from the site, that is, Mumbai Expressway

- Optimum Moisture Content for given soil sample is 6.90 %.
- Maximum Dry Density is 1.855 gm/cc.
- Liquid Limit for given soil sample is 31.10% and Plastic Limit is (Non-Plastic) due to sandy soil and Plasticity Index is Null for this soil sample.
- Free swell index for given soil sample is 16%.
- California Bearing Ratio (CBR) for given soil sample is 17.22%

Based on the research and results, the soil was deemed suitable for construction, with additional tests such as the California Bearing Ratio (CBR), Tri-axial Test, and Direct Shear Test recommended for further analysis.

After obtaining values from various soil samples, these were input into a program to assess structural stability using the Bishop Slope Stability Method. The analysis revealed an ultimate shear force of 311.81 kN (minimum required: 160.30 kN) and an ultimate moment of 539.27 kNm (minimum required: 216.86 kNm). The active force was calculated as 230.03 kN/m, while the passive force was 369.70 kN/m. The calculated CDR was 1.009, meeting the slope stability criteria according to the Bishop Slope Stability Method.

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